

Adjustment among College Students

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ABSTRACT:

For college students, adjustment required in various dimensions, which degree and type is varied with students depending on background, experience and prior schooling and environment of college. It's a process of finding and adopting modes of behavior suitable to the environment. Generally emotional and social adjusted students perform better. In present study adjustment of college students have been measured and comparatively analyzed.

Keywords: Adjustment ,Environment .

1. Introduction:

Education is the process of facilitating learning or acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. Adjustment is a behavioral process of balancing conflicting needs. More than 40% of all college entrants leave studies before completion. 75% of these students drop out in first 2 year of college. The transition from school to college has emotions, social and academic adjustment. Some students find ways and adapt it whereas other's feel overwhelmed and unable to meet the demands effectively.

Adjustment patterns of students differ with their level of intelligence. College students have adjustment problem in home also. They have difficulties with parents, siblings due to shyness, aggressiveness. They have academic adjustment problem due to new academic pattern, environment and faculties. Motivation to learn, taking action to meet academic demands and academic un satisfaction are components of academic adjustment. Social adjustment is important for students. Forming supportive network, managing new social freedom, home sickness, loneliness are social adjustment problems.

Quality of informal contact with faculty support and helps to make adjustment. Psychological distress, somatic distress, anxiety, low self esteem, depression have been cause of dropping out.

2. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY:

To find adjustment among college students of UG classes

To find adjustment among college students with respect to classes of UG

To find adjustment among college students of UG classes with respect to their gender

3. HYPOTHESIS:

There is significant adjustment among college students of UG classes.

There is no significant difference between adjustment values of college students with respect to UG class.

There is no significant difference between adjustment value of boys and girls college students of UG classes.

4. METHODOLOGY:

300 college students were selected randomly for study. In sample 100 students were from 1st year, 100 from 2nd year and 100 from 3rd year. In each group 50 boys and 50 girls were taken. All selected students were tested for adjustment using a self prepared test paper. In the test paper academic, social, emotional, environmental adjustment were taken.

5. FINDING AND ANALYSIS:

Table1. - Status of Adjustment among College Students

Class	Adjustment Status	No. of Students %	
		Male	Female
Graduation 1st Year	High	41	29
	Medium	27	32
	Low	32	39
Graduation 2nd Year	High	46	32
	Medium	35	39
	Low	19	29
Graduation 3rd Year	High	48	36
	Medium	39	43
	Low	13	21

Figure 1. Status of Adjustment among College Students

Majority of UG college students have good adjustment, 38.6% have high adjustment, 36% have medium adjustment and 25.6% students have low adjustment value. On the basis of this result hypothesis 1 there is significant adjustment among college students of UG classes is accepted.

UG 1st year, 2nd year and 3rd year comparison show that adjustment of 1st year student is rather than 2nd year and 3rd year students. Adjustment value is highest for 3rd year students. High adjustment is found in 35% of 1st year students, 39% in 2nd year students and 42% in 3rd year students. Medium adjustment showed by 29.5% in 1st year, 37% in 2nd year and 41% in 3rd year students. Low adjustment observed in 35.5% of 1st year, 24% of second year and 17% 3rd year students. The hypothesis 2 there is no significant difference between adjustment values of college students with respect to UG class is rejected.

College boys of UG classes have high adjustment rather than girls. 45% boys have high adjustment while girl's % is 33%. 34% boys and 35% girls showed medium adjustment. 22% boys and 29% girls exhibited low adjustment. Hence, hypothesis 3 there is no significant difference between adjustment value of boys and girls college students of UG classes is rejected.

6. CONCLUSION:

Most of the college students show good adjustment. Boy's adjustment is higher than girls and 3rd year students show highest adjustment. College students are adolescents have capability to do highest adjustment with so many dreams, lot of wishes to fulfill it, commitments and flexibility. They are mentally prepared for adjustment to reach at goal.

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